

THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF IMPROVING THE PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF FUTURE MUSIC TEACHERS

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Abstract: This thesis talks about the importance of improving the professional-pedagogical skills of music teachers and professional competence, which is considered one of its branches. Today, the effectiveness of music teachers' activities, preparation for starting pedagogical activities, first of all, the importance of pedagogical skills, the possession of the types of competences necessary in each pedagogical process, is highlighted in the activity.

Key words: musical culture, moral education, aesthetics, activity, pedagogy, pedagogical skill, competence, component, expert.

Introduction:

The goals and objectives of each subject taught in general secondary education are defined. The science of music culture, which is inextricably linked with practical activities, also has its own goals and tasks, and the main goal of teaching the science of music culture in secondary schools is the spiritual, artistic and moral development of students. It is to form culture, national pride and patriotism, to expand thinking, to develop creative skills, sophistication and artistic taste in children, and to educate initiative. The professional formation of a teacher begins with the process of obtaining professional education in higher education. The content of science programs of higher pedagogic universities is aimed at imparting professional knowledge to future teachers, teaching the secrets of pedagogic activity and creating skills in students. A skill is "a combination of personal characteristics of a person necessary to perform a job successfully"¹. The concept of pedagogical skills is defined differently in modern psychology and pedagogy. "A specialist with pedagogical skills is a specialist who is a skilled master of his profession, is highly cultured, has a deep knowledge of his subject, is able to analyze the fields of related sciences well, and has mastered the methodology of education and training perfectly"².

The concept of pedagogical skill is explained as follows:

1. High level of culture, high level of knowledge;
2. Possessor of excellent knowledge of his subject;

¹ Маркова А. К. Психология профессионализма. – М.: Знание, 1996. 26-бет

² Xoliqov A. "Pedagogik mahorat". Iqtisod-moliya nashriyoti, Toshkent., 2011-yil, 11-бет.

3. A person who can thoroughly master the knowledge of pedagogy and psychology and use them in his professional activity;

4. A pedagogue who perfectly knows the methodology of educational and educational work.

Pedagogical skill of a music teacher increases with the acquisition of various skills. That is, by describing the following skills that a music teacher needs to develop, we will better understand the process of his formation, the stages of achieving pedagogical skills:

First of all, he has professional organizational skills: always analyzing himself as a pedagogue, ensuring quick control over children's activities, taking into account the children's attitude to pedagogical influence, guiding the student in time. rational implementation of training and correction of given pedagogical tasks, fulfilling instructions to achieve set tasks, regulating relationships between children, encouraging activities taking into account children's successes and achievements, the most of the requirements in the lesson, learning such as finding the optimal form and changing them depending on the individual characteristics of children and specific pedagogical conditions, clear, short and easy explanation of tasks.

Secondly, analytical abilities: to analyze the obtained results in comparison with the initial data and pedagogical tasks, to analyze the nature of achievements and shortcomings in musical activity, to connect one's own experience with pedagogical theory based on the analysis of the achieved results, to prioritize pedagogical tasks thrust and grounding. It is necessary for a teacher to "constantly analyze his work and be critical of it"³.

Third, communication skills: the music teacher builds relationships with children and their parents, educates children morally, aesthetically, provides an individual approach to each child. After all, the basis of musical and educational activity is communication. The ability to communicate with children does not develop without love for them. Relationships in the team largely determine success in upbringing, education and training. This determines the content and importance of the teacher's communication skills.

Fourth, design skills: the ability to design the results of pedagogical activities, plan ways to implement them, design the mastery of music science for each child and group, the results of upbringing and education, which can occur in the musical education and training of children anticipating difficulties, distinguishing and formulating specific tasks.

³ Asqarova M., Xayitboyeva M., Nishonov M. Pedagogika. "Talqin" nashriyoti. Toshkent., 2008-yil. 37-bet.

Conclusion:

Summarizing the above, we note that the pedagogical activity of a future music teacher is special knowledge, skills and abilities, organizational skills, a high level of professional training, self-awareness in the profession, constant self- z-is to demonstrate the skills of self-improvement, communication and finding the right approach to each child. This is his future as a pedagogue, which will be established through his great interest in his work, understanding of his task, his place in art, high personal culture and professional passion. As we study the main components of pedagogical skills, we are convinced that all the above components are fully applicable to the professional activity of a music teacher. The formation of pedagogical skills in a music teacher is aimed at contributing to personal culture, timely and complete socialization of a growing person, and educating a child spiritually, morally and aesthetically.

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